
CSCCE Glossary: Nurturing Online Communities

Introduction

In the CSCCE course, [Nurturing Online Communities \(NOC\)](#), participants explore a variety of social science claims about how people behave in online communities to inform actions that STEM community managers might take to support increased engagement, commitment, and constructive behavior. This document is intended to offer some brief, non-academic definitions of some of the terminology used in the book [Building Successful Online Communities](#) by Kraut and Resnick, which is the course textbook for NOC. After each definition, we have included a reference to where a term first appears in the book, as well as any other relevant sources, as appropriate.

The terms defined in this document form part of our wider Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement (CSCCE) glossary, [a growing resource on our website](#), which also includes language from our other frameworks and courses. It is a work in progress, and we're adding new sections all the time. As we add new sections, we're also creating PDF records like this one, which you can cite if you find our definitions of terms helpful.

We welcome feedback on the terms included as well as suggestions of additions, and encourage you to [join the conversations](#) in our community of practice.

About CSCCE

The Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement (CSCCE) champions the importance of human infrastructure for effective collaboration in STEM. We provide training and support for the people who make scientific collaborations succeed at scale and we also research the impact of these emerging roles.

Find out more about us on our website: cscce.org

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This sub-section of the glossary was written by CSCCE staff members. CSCCE uses the CRediT contributor roles taxonomy to show how the authors listed contributed to the creation of this guide:

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ACTIVE SELF-DISCLOSURE

Occurs when members share personal information with other members. This can build bonds-based commitment. (Chapter 3, p. 94)

AFFECTIVE COMMITMENT

A type of commitment that emphasizes feelings of connection between members or to the group as a whole. It includes both bonds-based and identity-based commitment. (Chapter 3, p. 78)

BONDS-BASED COMMITMENT

A type of affective commitment that refers to how connected the members feel to each other in a community. (Chapter 3, p. 79)

BOOTSTRAPPING

Working to get to critical mass by leveraging the activities of existing members to attract new members. (Chapter 6, p. 249)

CARVING OUT A NICHE

The process by which a new community establishes the unique purpose and value that it creates within the context of a broader ecosystem. Involves defining the scope of the community, its relationship to other communities, and how people, activities, and content within the community will be organized. (Chapter 6, p. 232)

COERCED COMPLIANCE

Tactics for limiting inappropriate behavior to minimize the disruption by bad actors; includes throttles, activity quotas, gags, bans, and use of currency. (Chapter 4, p. 137)

COLLECTIVE EFFORT MODEL

A theoretical framework that explains when individuals are motivated to exert effort in group contexts. The model proposes that people's contributions to group activities depend on two key factors: how much they care about the group's success and how much they believe their personal efforts will meaningfully impact the group's overall performance and results. (Chapter 2, p. 62)

CONTRIBUTION GAP

The difference between the potential number of contributions and actual number of contributions that community members make in a community. (Chapter 1, p. 22)

COMPETITIVE ANALYSIS

An analysis to help designers consider the costs and benefits that members may experience when deciding between two similar online communities. Members may prefer to avoid switching costs associated with leaving an existing community for a new one unless the participation benefits of the new community are higher. (Chapter 6, p. 244)

DESCRIPTIVE NORM

Observed patterns of behavior that actually occur within a community, regardless of whether these behaviors are officially encouraged or discouraged. (Chapter 6, p. 144)

DESIGN CLAIM

A predictive statement that proposes a cause-and-effect relationship between specific design features and expected outcomes in online communities. Design claims assert that implementing particular design elements under certain conditions will likely produce specific results that support community objectives. Design claims function as bridges between academic theory and practical community design, offering evidence-based guidance for creating online environments while recognizing that outcomes depend on various factors and may require testing and refinement.

DESIGN GOALS

The intended positive outcomes or characteristics that community designers aim to achieve in online spaces. These goals represent the ideal qualities and results that indicate a successful, well-functioning digital community. (Chapter 1, p. 12)

DESIGN LEVER

Technical and social configurations that community managers can use to influence the behavior of members. These include: community structure; content, tasks, and activities; selecting, sorting and highlighting; external communication; feedback, rewards, and sanctions; roles, rules, and guidelines; access controls; and presentation and framing. (Chapter 1, p. 6)

ENDORSEMENTS

Public testimonials about the community, usually by celebrities or individuals with high status. Can be used to increase contributions and commitment to the community. (Chapter 5, p. 190)

ENTRY BARRIERS

Tasks that a prospective member must complete before joining; can help build commitment among new members. (Chapter 5, pp. 111, 183)

EXPECTANCY-VALUE THEORY

A motivational theory that explains individual effort as the product of two key factors: the likelihood that actions will produce desired results and the personal importance of those results. According to this theory, people are motivated to exert effort when they both believe their actions can successfully achieve an outcome and when that outcome matters to them. (Chapter 2, p. 23; see also Vroom 1995, Porter and Lawler 2005)

EXTRINSIC MOTIVATION

Motivation driven by external rewards or consequences rather than inherent satisfaction from the activity itself. This type of motivation occurs when individuals engage in behaviors primarily to obtain something they want, or to avoid something they don't want, rather than because they find the activity personally fulfilling or enjoyable. (Chapter 2, p. 24)

FACE-SAVING INTERVENTIONS

Offering inappropriate actors an opportunity to explain their intent and correct their behavior rather than punishing them. (Chapter 4, p. 152)

FOCUS THEORY

A social psychological theory developed by Robert Cialdini that proposes that norms influence behavior only when they are "focused" (made salient or prominent) in a given situation. (Chapter 4, p. 143)

GRADUATED SANCTIONS

Sequential consequences for inappropriate behavior. (Chapter 4, p. 162)

HALO EFFECT

A cognitive bias in which an overall impression of a person, company, brand, or product influences opinions about their specific qualities or characteristics. When someone has a positive general impression, they tend to evaluate specific attributes more favorably than they would objectively warrant, and vice versa for negative impressions. (Chapter 5, p. 189)

HEURISTIC PROCESSING

A mode of information processing characterized by the use of mental shortcuts, rules of thumb, or simplified decision-making strategies to quickly evaluate information and make judgments. Heuristic processing prioritizes efficiency and speed over thoroughness and accuracy. (Chapter 5, p. 189)

HIGH STATUS INDIVIDUALS

Members of a community who are perceived to have high social capital and may be more influential in asking other members to contribute. (Chapter 2, p. 31)

IDENTITY-BASED COMMITMENT

A type of affective commitment that refers to how close the members feel to the community as a whole and/or the community's purpose. (Chapter 3, p. 79)

INTERPERSONAL RECRUITING

A membership growth strategy where current community members personally reach out to potential new members with direct invitations to join. This approach relies on existing members taking initiative to identify, contact, and encourage specific individuals to become part of the community. This method creates a direct connection between recruiter and recruit, often making the invitation more personal and persuasive than anonymous outreach efforts. (Chapter 5, p. 183)

INTRINSIC MOTIVATION

Motivation that arises from internal satisfaction and personal fulfillment derived from an activity itself. This type of motivation occurs when individuals engage in behaviors because they find the activity naturally rewarding, enjoyable, or meaningful, rather than to achieve external rewards or outcomes. (Chapter 2, p. 24)

MATCH VALUE

The perceived benefit or worth that an individual expects to gain from participating in a particular online community or digital opportunity. This represents how well a person believes an online interaction will meet their needs, interests, or goals. (Chapter 6, p. 234)

NEEDS-BASED COMMITMENT

Also known as continuance commitment. A type of commitment that emphasizes the benefits that members receive from the community. (Chapter 3, p. 105)

NORMATIVE BEHAVIOR

Behavior that conforms to established social norms, standards, or expectations within a particular group, culture, or context. Normative behavior represents actions that are considered typical, appropriate, or socially acceptable by members of a community. (Chapter 4, p. 125)

NORMATIVE COMMITMENT

A type of commitment that emphasizes feelings of member loyalty and obligation to the community. (Chapter 3, p. 103)

ONBOARDING PATHWAYS

The series of actions usually taken by a community manager or community champions to welcome new members to a community. These can include sharing information about community programming and the community platform, as well as a welcome call and/or welcome survey to learn more about the new member's needs and interests. Onboarding typically consists of several phases; the recruit, select, socialize and maintain stages. (Chapter 5, pp. 205-217)

ONLINE COMMUNITIES

Virtual spaces where people come together to interact, share information, learn from each other, and participate in social experiences. (Chapter 1, p. 1)

PERFORMANCE-CONTINGENT REWARDS

Benefits or prizes that are awarded to members based on the quality of their contributions. (Chapter 2, p. 53)

PRESENTATION AND FRAMING

A design lever that emphasizes how information about the community and its activities is conveyed and communicated. (Chapter 1, p. 8)

PROCEDURAL JUSTICE

The perceived fairness of the processes, methods, and procedures used to make decisions and allocate resources, rather than the fairness of the outcomes themselves. Procedural justice focuses on *how* decisions are made rather than *what* decisions are reached. (Chapter 4, p. 132)

PROCESSING THEORY

A decision-making theory proposing that the level of care or concern individuals have about a particular area directly influences how thoroughly they analyze their options. When people consider a decision domain highly important or personally relevant, they are more likely to engage in detailed evaluation of the costs and benefits before making their choice. (Chapter 2, p. 30)

PRODUCT DIFFUSION

The process by which a new product, innovation, or technology spreads and is adopted throughout a market or population over time. Product diffusion describes how innovations move from initial introduction to widespread acceptance across different consumer segments. (Chapter 5, p. 184)

PUBLIC GOODS PROBLEM

A social dilemma that arises when individuals have incentives to under-contribute to or free-ride on

goods that benefit everyone, leading to their disinvestment and/or deterioration. The problem stems from the inherent characteristics of public goods and the rational self-interest of individuals. (Chapter 4, p. 129)

PUSH VS. PULL

A strategic design consideration regarding how community members discover and access new content. This framework examines whether updates and information should be actively delivered to users (push) or whether users should actively seek out new content themselves (pull). (Chapter 6, p. 234)

READER-TO-LEADER FUNNEL

A strategic framework describing the progressive pathway through which community members advance from passive content consumers to active leaders and contributors within online communities or content platforms. The funnel maps the journey of increasing engagement and responsibility over time. (Chapter 5, p. 182)

REGULATION

The formal and informal mechanisms, rules, and processes used to govern behavior, maintain order, and enforce community standards within digital spaces. Regulation encompasses both top-down control systems and emergent social control mechanisms that shape how members interact. (Chapter 4, p. 131)

SANDBOXES

Test environments where new members can learn how to do something before gaining full access; provides training to new members while also protecting the larger community. (Chapter 5, p. 218)

SCREENING / VERIFICATION

The processes and mechanisms used to authenticate user identities, validate credentials, or assess member qualifications before granting access to community features, content, or privileges. These systems help ensure community quality, safety, and alignment with the community's intended purpose. (Chapter 4, p. 131)

SELF-DETERMINATION THEORY

A motivational theory proposing that individuals develop greater intrinsic interest and engagement in activities when their environment supports feelings of competence and autonomy. According to this theory, people are naturally motivated to pursue tasks that allow them to feel skilled and capable, while also experiencing a sense of choice and self-direction. (Chapter 2, p. 59)

SELF-SELECTION

The process by which potential members evaluate and determine whether an online community aligns with their interests, values, or needs before deciding to join. This involves prospective members actively assessing the community's culture, content, membership, and overall environment to judge their compatibility. (Chapter 5, p. 198)

SOCIAL CONTACT

Combining tasks to do within a community with social interaction. This can increase members' willingness to contribute, especially if the tasks are tedious. (Chapter 2, p. 42)

SOCIAL DILEMMA

Situations in which it's better for everyone if everyone complies with a social norm - but each individual can "free ride" and end up better off if they defy the norm while everyone else is still complying with it. The dilemma is what you as an individual should do when you know this. (Chapter 4, p. 129)

SOCIAL PROOF

A psychological principle and persuasion technique where individuals use others' behavior as a guide for determining appropriate or valuable actions. This mental shortcut leads people to view something as worthwhile or correct when they observe that others are doing it or supporting it. Social proof operates on the assumption that if many people are engaging in a particular behavior or holding a specific belief, it must be the right thing to do. (Chapter 2, p. 35; see also Cialdini 2001)

SOCIALIZATION TACTICS

The methods that communities use to help newcomers understand and adapt to the community's culture, norms, and practices. These tactics guide new members through the process of learning how the community operates and what's expected of them. These methods can include institutionalized practices (e.g., formal, universal training programs) and more individualized approaches. (Chapter 5, p. 211)

SWITCHING COSTS

The costs a member incurs when moving from one community to a new one. (Chapter 6, p. 244)

SYSTEMATIC PROCESSING

A mode of information processing characterized by careful, deliberate, and thorough evaluation of information and arguments. Systematic processing involves effortful cognitive analysis where individuals carefully consider the quality, logic, and evidence of the information presented. (Chapter 5, p. 189)

TASK-CONTINGENT REWARDS

Benefits or prizes that are awarded to members for the completion of an activity, regardless of the quality. (Chapter 2, p. 53)

THROTTLES / QUOTA MECHANISMS

Technical and policy-based controls that limit the frequency, volume, or rate of specific user actions within a defined time period. These mechanisms prevent abuse, manage resources, and maintain community quality by constraining how much or how often users can perform certain activities. (Chapter 4, p. 136)

TRAGEDY OF THE COMMONS

A social dilemma that results in the degradation or collapse of shared digital resources and community quality when individual users act in their own self-interest at the expense of the collective good. This phenomenon adapts Garrett Hardin's classic economic concept to online environments, where shared community resources can be undervalued, overused, or abused. (Chapter 4, p. 129)

VOLUNTARY COMPLIANCE

The willingness of community members to follow rules, norms, and behavioral expectations without coercion, external enforcement, or direct monitoring. Voluntary compliance represents self-regulated adherence to community standards based on internalized values, social pressure, or perceived legitimacy rather than fear of punishment. (Chapter 4, p. 140)

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